

(Table 1 contd.)

3a	$C_6H_5CH=$ H_2C	277	55	$C_{29}H_{19}NO$
3b	H_2C H_2C $C=$	235	60	$C_{24}H_{19}NO$
3c	C_6H_5 C_6H_5 $C=$	194	60	$C_{29}H_{21}NO$
3d	$C_6H_5-CH=CH-CH=$	230	50	$C_{30}H_{21}NO$
3e		239	40	$C_{26}H_{17}NO_2$

*All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

Azomethines of 10-p-aminobenzylidene anthrone :

10-p-Aminobenzylidene anthrone : 10-p-Nitrobenzylidene anthrone (3.27 g, 0.01 mol ; prepared by the reported method^a) was refluxed with $SnCl_2$ (8 g) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) and concentrated HCl (20 ml) was added for 0.5 h. The reflux was continued for further 3 h and the hot reaction mixture was poured slowly with stirring in ice-cold 40% NaOH solution (100 ml). The copious precipitate was digested in the ether solution to remove excess $SnCl_2$ and filtered hot and washed free of NaOH by water. The resulting solid was dried and crystallised from aqueous ethanol (50%) (Found : C, 84.14 ; H, 5.03 ; N, 4.7. Calcd. for : C, 84.85 ; H, 5.05 ; N, 4.71%). The presence of the primary amine was confirmed by diazotisation of the compound to produce an orange coloured dye.

Azomethines of 10-p-aminobenzylidene anthrone (3) : A new series of azomethines were prepared by condensing different aldehydes and ketones with 10-p-aminobenzylidene anthrone. 10-p-Aminobenzylidene anthrone (0.295 g, 0.001 mol) was refluxed for 3 h with equimolar quantity of the respective aldehyde or ketone in methanol or ethanol (15 ml) and glacial acetic acid (1 drop). The hot solution was cooled and kept overnight, and the resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from methanol or ethanol ; ν_{max} 1 660 (C=N) and 1 680 cm^{-1} (C=O).

Anticancer activity : Anticancer activity tests^a were carried out on P-83 (ovarian) tumor *in situ*. Compounds 1 indicated intense anticancer activity, while compounds 2 and 3 did not show any activity. These facts indicate that the presence of azomethine group stabilised by aromatic ring shows anticancer activity. Azomethine compounds containing C=O or $-CH=CH-$ group or both do not reveal anticancer activity.

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Studies on Pyrazolines. Part-II. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 1H-3-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-n-butoxy-5-nitrophen-1'-yl)-5-substituted-phenyl-2-pyrazolines and related Compounds

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IN view of the biological activity of pyrazoline derivatives¹ and in continuation of our earlier work², the synthesis of pyrazolines 2 and their derivatives (3, 4 and 5) was undertaken.

In the present communication previously reported 2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcones (1)² on condensation with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol gave 1H-3-(2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrophen-1'-yl)-5-substituted-phenyl-2-pyrazolines (2). The reaction of 2 with benzoyl chloride gave the benzoyl derivatives (3). Similarly, the reaction of 2 with acetic acid gave the acetyl derivatives (4) by direct and indirect methods. Further, the reactions of the pyrazolines (2) with various sulphonyl chlorides afforded the corresponding sulphonamide derivatives (5) (Scheme 1). The structures of the compounds have been supported by elemental and ir spectral data.

The compounds 2 revealed the following ir bands : 2 3 500-3 400 (OH), 3 340-3 320 (NH), 1 620-1 600 (C=N), 1 240-1 220 (C-N) and 1 380-1 370 cm^{-1} (CH_2 of pyrazoline) ; 3 3 500-3 350 (OH), 1 660-1 650 (C=O, N-C=O), 1 610-1 590 (C=N) and 1 230-1 220 cm^{-1} (C-N) ; 4 3 500-3 350 (OH), 1 670-1 660 (C=O, N-C=O), 1 615-1 600 (C=N) and 1 230-1 220 cm^{-1} (C-N) ; 5 3 500-3 350 (OH), 1 610-1 600 (C=N), 1 300-1 290, 1 145-1 140 (S=O sym and asym, respectively) and 1 230-1 220 cm^{-1} (C-N).

The compounds exhibited pmr peaks at : 2 δ 3.00-3.20 (1H, dd, CH_2 of pyrazoline ring), 3.60-3.80 (1H, dd, CH_2 of pyrazoline ring), 4.80-5.10 (1H, dd, CH of pyrazoline ring) and 6.8-8.1 (m, ArH and NH), integration of signals at δ 3.0-5.1 ($CHCH_2$ group of pyrazoline ring) ; 3 δ 2.8-3.6 (CH_2 of pyrazoline ring), 4.90-5.20 (CH of pyrazoline ring) and 7.45-8.5 (ArH) ; 4 δ 2.7-3.5 (CH_2 of pyrazoline ring), 4.8-5.1 (CH of pyrazoline ring) and 7.30-8.3 (ArH) ; 5 δ 3.0-3.8 (CH_2 of pyrazoline ring), 5.0-5.3 (CH of pyrazoline ring) 7.50-8.6 (ArH).

NOTES

R = Aryl

Scheme 1

- R = Aryl
 (i) Ar = 4-Tolyl
 (ii) Ar = 4-Aminophenyl
 (iii) Ar = 4-Chlorophenyl
 (iv) Ar = 4-Acetamidophenyl

Antimicrobial activity : The antimicrobial screening of all the compounds were carried out using cup-plate⁸ method at a concentration of 50 µg ml⁻¹ using gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* and fungus *Aspergillus niger*.

Most of the compounds showed activity against different strains of bacteria and the fungus (6–20 mm, zone of inhibition). Compounds 2–5 were found to be active against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* and the zone of inhibition being 6–12, 7–14, 6–14 and 10–20 mm, respectively. It was observed that sulphonamide derivatives (5) of pyrazoline are more active against both bacteria and the fungus than the pyrazolines (2) and their benzoyl (3) and acetyl (4) derivatives. The presence of bromine/chlorine atom in the nucleus is responsible for the increase of antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

Melting points of the compounds were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected.

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu DR-1, 435-IR spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a XL-100A (100.1 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal reference standard.

1H-3-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrophen-1'-yl)-5 phenyl-2-pyrazoline (2a) : A mixture of 1-(2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrophen-1'-yl)-3-phenyl-2-propen-1-one (1; 0.01 mol) and 99% hydrazine hydrate (0.015 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed gently for 2 h. The mixture was then concentrated and allowed to cool. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with ethanol and recrystallised from ethanol to give a pale brown solid (80%), m p. 150° (Found : C, 52.55; H, 4.57; N, 9.65 C₁₉H₂₀O₄N₃Br requires : C, 52.53; H, 4.60; N, 9.68%). Similarly, other pyrazolines were prepared (Table 1).

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Sl. no.	R	M p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
2a	Phenyl	150	80	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₃ Br
2b	2'-Chlorophenyl	165	85	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₃ BrCl
2c	4'-Chlorophenyl	172	84	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₃ BrCl
2d	2',4'-Dichlorophenyl	180	88	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₃ BrCl ₂
2e	4'-Methylphenyl	160	75	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₃ Br
2f	3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl	95	78	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₃ Br
2g	3',4',5'-Trimethoxyphenyl	175	70	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₇ N ₃ Br
2h	3',4'-Dimethoxyphenyl	100	73	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₃ Br
2i	4'-Methoxyphenyl	130	75	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₅ N ₃ Br
2j	2'-Methoxyphenyl	145	65	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₅ N ₃ Br
2k	4'-N-Dimethylamino-phenyl	110	62	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₄ Br
3a	Phenyl	190	82	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₃ Br
3b	2'-Chlorophenyl	200	84	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ O ₅ N ₃ Br
3c	4'-Chlorophenyl	220	85	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ O ₅ N ₃ BrCl
3d	2',4'-Dichlorophenyl	210	80	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₃ BrCl ₂
3e	4'-Methylphenyl	180	70	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ O ₅ N ₃ Br
3f	3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl	115	75	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₇ N ₃ Br
3g	3',4',5'-Trimethoxyphenyl	178	78	C ₃₀ H ₃₀ O ₈ N ₃ Br
3h	3',4'-Dimethoxyphenyl	150	72	C ₂₈ H ₂₈ O ₇ N ₃ Br
3i	4'-Methoxyphenyl	127	65	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ O ₆ N ₃ Br
3j	2'-Methoxyphenyl	135	72	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ O ₆ N ₃ Br
3k	4'-N-Dimethylaminophenyl	185	68	C ₂₈ H ₃₀ O ₅ N ₄ Br
4a	Phenyl	165	90	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₅ N ₃ Br
4b	2'-Chlorophenyl	160	93	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₃ BrCl
4c	4'-Chlorophenyl	180	90	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₃ BrCl
4d	2',4'-Dichlorophenyl	120	88	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₃ BrCl ₂
4e	4'-Methylphenyl	160	78	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₃ Br
4f	3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl	134	80	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₇ N ₃ Br
4g	3',4',5'-Trimethoxyphenyl	157	85	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ O ₈ N ₃ Br
4h	3',4'-Dimethoxyphenyl	142	82	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₇ N ₃ Br
4i	4'-Methoxyphenyl	190	76	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₃ Br
4j	2'-Methoxyphenyl	152	70	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₃ Br
4k	4'-N-Dimethylamino-phenyl	112	75	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₅ N ₄ Br
(i) Ar = 4-Tolyl				
5a	Phenyl	125	80	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₆ N ₃ BrS
5b	2'-Chlorophenyl	170	75	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₃ BrClS
5c	4'-Methylphenyl	180	72	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ O ₆ N ₃ BrS
5d	3',4'-Methylenedioxy-phenyl	155	77	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₃ BrS
5e	4'-Methoxyphenyl	140	70	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ O ₇ N ₃ BrS
(ii) Ar = 4-Aminophenyl				
5f	Phenyl	135	83	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₆ N ₄ BrS
5g	2'-Chlorophenyl	162	85	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₄ BrClS
5h	4'-Methylphenyl	187	75	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₆ N ₄ BrS
5i	3',4'-Methylenedioxy-phenyl	118	72	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₈ N ₄ BrS
5j	4'-Methoxyphenyl	146	65	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₇ N ₄ BrS

(Table 1 contd.)

(iii) Ar=4-Chlorophenyl				
5k	Phenyl	166	75	$C_{26}H_{23}O_6N_3BrClS$
5l	2'-Chlorophenyl	145	78	$C_{26}H_{22}O_6N_3BrCl_2S$
5m	4'-Methylphenyl	105	82	$C_{26}H_{25}O_6N_3BrClS$
5n	3',5'-Methylenedioxyphenyl	180	80	$C_{26}H_{22}O_8N_3BrClS$
5o	4'-Methoxyphenyl	190	87	$C_{26}H_{25}O_7N_3BrClS$
(iv) Ar=4-Acetamidophenyl				
5p	Phenyl	205	86	$C_{27}H_{27}O_7N_4BrS$
5q	2'-Chlorophenyl	127	72	$C_{27}H_{26}O_7N_4BrClS$
5r	4'-Methylphenyl	140	74	$C_{27}H_{29}O_7N_4BrNS$
5s	3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl	180	80	$C_{28}H_{27}O_9N_4BrS$
5t	4'-Methoxyphenyl	119	85	$C_{28}H_{29}O_8N_4BrS$

*N (and S) analysis found satisfactory.

1-Benzoyl-3-(2''-hydroxy-3''-bromo-4''-n-butoxy-5''-nitrophen-1''-yl)-5-phenyl-2-pyrazoline (3a): A mixture of **2a** (0.001 mol) and benzoyl chloride (0.0011 mol) was dissolved in dry pyridine (10 ml) and stirred at room temperature for 1 h, after which the reaction mixture was treated with cold dilute HCl (2N). The resulting solid was filtered and washed successively with water, cold NaOH (2%) and water, and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid (82%), m.p. 190° (Found: C, 58.04; H, 4.42; N, 7.75. $C_{36}H_{34}O_8N_8Br$ requires: C, 57.99; H, 4.46; N, 7.80%).

Similarly, other benzoyl derivatives were prepared (Table 1).

1-Acetyl-3-(2''-hydroxy-3''-bromo-4''-n-butoxy-5''-nitrophen-1''-yl)-5-phenylpyrazoline (4a). Indirect method: A mixture of **2a** (0.001 mol) and acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The solution was then concentrated. On cooling, the resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol (90%), m.p. 165° (Found: C, 52.90; H, 4.65; N, 8.86. $C_{31}H_{32}O_8N_8Br$ requires: C, 52.94; H, 4.62; N, 8.82%). Similarly, other acetyl derivatives were prepared (Table 1).

Direct method: A mixture of the chalcone (**1**; 0.0015 mol) and 99% hydrazine hydrate (0.002 mol) in acetic acid (15 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the residual matter diluted with water. The resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol (80%), m.p. 165°. Analytical and spectroscopic data were identical with the sample prepared by indirect method.

1-p-Tolyl sulphonyl-3-(2''-hydroxy-3''-bromo-4''-n-butoxy-5''-nitrophen-1''-yl)-5-phenylpyrazoline (5a): A solution of **2a** (0.001 mol) in dry pyridine (10 ml) was cooled in an ice-bath and to it *p*-tolyl sulphonyl chloride (0.0011 mol) was added. The mixture was stirred for 1 h at room temperature and was then treated with cold dilute HCl (2N). The resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol (75%), m.p. 125° (Found: C, 53.11; H, 4.38; N, 7.17; $C_{36}H_{36}O_8N_8BrS$ requires: C, 53.06; H, 4.42; N, 7.14%).

Similarly, other sulphonamide derivatives were prepared (Table 1).

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Synthesis of some New Arylazopyrazoles and Arylazopyrimidines

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IN view of the important biological activities displayed by pyrazoles^{1,2}, pyrimidines³ and azo group⁴, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise some arylazo derivatives of pyrazoles and pyrimidines.

The arylazopyrazoles (**1**) and arylazopyrimidines (**2**) have been synthesised⁵ by reacting 2-arylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutan-1,3-diones (A) with thiosemicarbazide and guanidine nitrate respectively.

